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Traces of Śivadharma and Śivadharmottara in the Śivadharma Texts in Odisha

Dr. Anil Kumar Acharya¹

Abstract

Śivadharma (Śivadharmaśāstra) and Śivadharmottara are two authoritative texts of the Śivadharma corpus, believed to be composed before twelfth century A.D. and has pan-India presence. Manuscripts of this corpus are also found in Nepal and these texts have their influence in South Asian regions. Odisha, being fairly a land of Śaiva tradition, has produced many Śaiva scriptures, viz. *Ekāmra Purāṇa*, *Ekāmra-candrikā*, *Svarṇādri-mahodaya*, *Kapilasamhitā*, Śaivacintāmaṇi and Śaivakalpadruma etc. And these texts seem to have been influenced by these Śivadharma texts, especially by *Śivadahrma* and *Śivadharmottara*. But till date no research has been done to trace the Śivadharma and *Śivadharmottara* in the proper Śaiva scriptures of Odisha. Therefore, an attempt has been made to bring forth the traces of Śivadharma and *Śivadharmottara* in the aforementioned Śaiva scriptures of Odisha.

Key Words

Śivadharma corpus, Odisha, Śaivism

Introduction

Śivadharma (Śivadharmaśāstra) and *Śivadharmottara* are two authoritative texts on Śaivism and are two earliest texts of the eight constituent texts of the Śivadharma corpus. Texts in this corpus include - *Śivadharmaśāstra*, *Śivadharmottara*, *Śivadharmasaṅgraha*, *Śivopaniṣad*, *Umāmaheśvarasaṃvāda*, *Uttarottaramahāsaṃvāda*, *Vṛṣasārasaṅgraha*, and *Dharmaputrikā*. These are composed before the twelfth century A.D. and the composition of most of these texts is believed to be started in the era of the supremacy of Śaivism, i.e. after

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the sixth century A.D., over its rival Buddhism. These texts preach Śaiva religion for lay Śaivites, thus in general these texts have been considered texts of Paurāṇic or Āgamic corpus. These texts have a pan-Indian presence; also these are available in Nepal and have their influence in South Asian regions. This corpus is considered to be very important in the study of Śaivism. R.C. Hazra is the first scholar to publish two separate articles on Śivadharmā and Śivadharmottara in the Vols. X and XIII of the Journal of the Ganganatha Jha Research Institute, in the year 1952-53. After that, a Ph.D. thesis on the text Śivadharmasaṅgraha of this corpus has been submitted to the Pondicherry University by me in the year 2010. And recently a team of Indian, western and Nepali scholars are working on a mission mode to explore different aspects of this corpus under the foreign-funded project titled “The Śivadharmā Project ” from the year 2018.

Śaivism is one of the ancient religions of Odisha, which came into prominence by the end of the 6th century A.D, during the time of King Śaśāṅka of Gauḍa, a staunch follower of Śiva who has destroyed several Buddhist monuments and revived Hinduism by patronizing Śaiva religion. He is believed to be the founder of the Ekāmraṣṭra (old Bhubaneswar), the location of the present-day Liṅgarāja temple. Thereafter, the supremacy of this Śaiva religion was continued during the period of Bhaumas and followed by the Kesari dynasty from the ninth century A.D till the advent of Gaṅgas in the twelfth century A.D. Therefore, imprecisely seventh to twelfth century A.D could be considered as the golden era of the history of Śaivism in Odisha. During this period many grand and brilliant temples dedicated to Lord Śiva, viz. Mukteśvara, Rājarāṇi, Siddheśvara, Brahmeśvara, Liṅgarāja etc., were came into existence. Due to the ample number and eye-catching nature of those monuments scholars, while discussing the Śaivism of Odisha, often mainly focuses on these historical pieces of evidence, rather than exploring the surviving literature of that religion written by the native authors. We do not have enough surviving scriptures of ancient times about the Śaivism of Odisha. Available scriptures, either published or unpublished, are of late origin, i.e. post the 12th century. Few texts in praise of the importance of Ekāmraṣṭra and practices that prevailed in the temple therein are written in Sanskrit, viz. *Ekāmra Purāṇa* (thirteenth - fifteenth century A. D.), *Ekāmra-*

candrikā, *Svarṇādri-mahodaya*, *Kapilasamhitā* of anonymous authorship and Lakshmidhara Mishra's (seventeenth century A. D.) Śaivacintāmaṇi, Śaivakalpadruma and Śivāmṛtsārasamuccaya of Śrīśadeva.

Therefore, herein Śaiva scriptures proper of Odisha would be briefed, which are *Paurāṇic* or ritualistic and relatively less known or less studied. And considering the importance of the study of Śivadharmā tradition and Odisha being fairly a land of Śaiva tradition, herein an attempt would be made to bring forth the traces of Śivadharmā and Śivadharmottara in the aforementioned Śaiva scriptures of Odisha.

Śaiva scriptures proper of Odisha

Ekāmra Purāṇa, *Ekāmra-candrikā*, *Svarṇādri-mahodaya*, *Kapilasamhitā* of anonymous authorship, and Lakshmidhara Mishra's (seventeenth century A. D.) Śaivacintāmaṇi and Śaivakalpadruma have been considered by me as proper Śaiva scriptures of Odisha. Because, unlike the *kāvya*s or *mahākāvya*s on Odishan Śaivism like Śaivalīlāmṛta, etc, according to my belief these *Paurāṇic* and ritualistic texts present a historical and applied features of Odishan Śaivism.

The First four texts could be considered as *sthala Purāṇa*s narrating the glory of Ekāmraṣṭetra, the famous Śaiva pilgrimage of Odisha. They also record the cultural, religious and historical traditions prevailing at the then Ekāmraṣṭetra. *Ekāmra-purāṇa*, the earliest of these four texts, is believed to be composed during the thirteenth - fifteenth century A.D.². It gives a comprehensive description of Ekāmraṣṭetra comprising seventy *adhyāya*s and

2 "Because of its copious references in Gadadhara's Kalasara and in the Uttara Khanda of the Bengal recension of the Siva Purana he (R. C. Hazra) inclined to fix the date of its composition between C 950 A. D. and 1150 A.D. On the other hand, in view of the occurrence of Ananta-Vasudeva temple, which was built by 1278 A. D. and the reference to Mahapattra as the designation of a high officer during the Ganga period, which was first accepted by Kpilendra Deva before he was crowned as the first King of Gajapati dynasty, K. C. Panigrahi attempts to date the text to the fourteenth century A.D. Besides these, probably the scholars concerned failed to take note of one Siva shrine named after Kapilendra Deva (1435 – 1467 A.D.), which is popularly known as Kapilesvara. Though the work refers to certain events and traditions, which are much earlier than the actual date of its composition, the upper age limit of the work can be held to be as old as the 15th century A. D." – Dhal, U. N., 1986, pp.2-3.

claims to have six thousand verses. Also it presents itself as one of the eighteen Upapurāṇas by including it among the names of the eighteen Upapurāṇas in its very first chapter. Scholars like R. C. Hazara (1950, 70-76) and Ayodhya Prasad Saha (1976, 9) have opined that *Ekāmrapurāṇa* was compiled by the Āgamic Pāsupatas. *Ekāmra-candrikā*, *Svarṇādri-mahodaya*, and *Kapilasamhitā* contain fifteen, thirty-one and twenty-one *adhyāyas* respectively, and are comparatively smaller in size.

Śaivacintāmaṇi and Śaivakalpadruma are manuals for Śaiva priests, and both have been composed by the same author named Lakshmidhara Mishra. In the year 1994 Dukhisyama Pattanayak of Odisha published an edition of Śaivacintāmaṇi. It describes a Śaivite's daily divine practices (*nityācāras*) and *nyāsa*, *japa*, *dhyāna*, *mudrā*, *āvahana* & *visarjana* pertaining to temple worship (*pūjāpaddhatis*) in eight chapters (*paṭalas*). The Śaivakalpadruma is a *nibandha* text and is complete in eight chapters (*kāṇḍas*). Citing passages from different texts, Śaivakalpadruma records - the glorification of Śiva, the rite of initiation (*dīkṣā*), daily personal rite (*nityācāra*), various types of *liṅgas*, and their varied way of worship (*śivaliṅga-pūjāvidhi*), the process of regulations of breath (*prāṇāyāma*) as well as application of ashes (*bhaṣma*) on the various parts of the body, ceremonies and rites to be performed during various annual festivals connected with Śiva, and the construction of Śaiva temples and their consecration. The Śaivakalpadruma seems to be an unpublished text yet, but some research works on this text have been done by different scholars of Odisha³. It has been observed that Śaivakalpadruma has cited, directly and interestedly without mentioning the source, passages from Śaivacintāmaṇi⁴. Therefore, it is assumed that Śaivacintāmaṇi

3 "An article titled "Some Remarks on the unpublished Ritual Literature of Odisha and the Śaivakalpadruma of Lakṣmīdhara" by Dr. G. C. Tripathi; a Vidyāvaridhi (Ph.D.) thesis submitted to Rashtriya Sanskrit Sansthan, Puri Campus, in the year 1991, titled "Lakṣmīdharamiśra-kṛta Śaivakalpadrumasaya Samiḥṣātmakam Sampādanam" by Mamata Mahapatra - http://www.sanskrit.nic.in/Thesis_Modified/directory/L/11.htm . And a soft copy of the same is in my position; and an article by me titled "Dīkṣāvidhi as described in the Śaivakalpadruma" presented in the 15th World Sanskrit Conference....." - Acharya, Anil Kumar, 2014, p.390

4 "Between these two, ŚCM is earlier than ŚKD. For, the later had drawn on the earlier in presenting five sections of the second chapter, viz. Mantropadeśa in

is earlier than Śaivakalpadruma. It has been assumed by Dukhisayama Pattanayak that the time of the composition of Śaivacintāmaṇi could be the last decade of the 17th century (Pattanayak xxxi), and according to G. C. Tripathi the probable date of composition of Śaivakalpadruma is around 1675 A.D (Tripathi 263)

Besides, the text Śivāmṛtasārasamuccaya is an unpublished text believed to be composed not before the seventeenth century A. D.⁵ The author of this text is Śrīśadeva, who introduces himself as born in the family of Budhadeva, the chief treasurer of a certain king of Gauḍa region. This text is in the form of a compendium compiling passages from *Mahābhārata*, *Purāṇas*, *Rāmāyaṇa*, texts of Pāśupata, etc. on various topics related to the Śaiva religion and is complete in forty chapters. To date, two manuscripts of this text have been traced, of which one is a palm-leaf MS, with a slight variant title: Śaivāmṛtasārasamuccaya, which is preserved at Orissa State Museum (OSM), bearing no. D/225 (Mishra 1971, 157-58) and another is a paper MS titled Śivāmṛtasārasamuccaya preserved in Govt. Oriental Manuscript Library (GOML), Madras, bearing no. 5125. Of these

absence of Guru, Dakṣiṇāmūrtilingalakṣaṇa, Sthānanirṇaya for puraścaraṇa, Japakartuḥ bhakṣyābhakṣyanirṇaya in puraścaraṇa rite & Mantrasaṃkhyā. Subject matter presented in the first section is existent in ŚCM (1:26); presenting the second section ŚKD cites a verse which is attributed to certain Āgama, but the same verse could be located in ŚCM (5:57); third section cites a verse which has been attributed to Cintāmaṇi and that very verse is in ŚCM (1:27-28); fourth section quotes a verse, without mentioning its source, which is found in ŚCM (1:29); and the fifth section quotes a half verse which has been attributed to ŚCM, but unfortunately I could not locate that line in the published edition of ŚCM. It is evident from the above deliberation that ŚKD has drawn on ŚCM twice directly and thrice indirectly without mentioning the source.”- *ibid*, pp.390-391

- 5 “But in general, it could be assumed that this literary creation of Śrīśadeva could not have been composed before 17th century A. D. For, the author quotes *Ekāmrapurāṇa*, one of the oldest Śaiva paurāṇic works of Odisha. The upper age limit of *Ekāmrapurāṇa* is believed to be 15th century A.D. Besides, ŚASS cites passages from *Kapilasamhitā*, another notable *Sthalapurāṇa* of Odisha. And it is assumed that the composition of *Kapilasamhitā* cannot be later than the middle part of the 16th century A.D. Also the author has cited passages attributed to certain *anantabhaṭṭī tīkā* in the context of *Śivarātrivrata*, and, in identification of this *Ananta Bhatta*, references are available of few *Ananta Bhatta-s* all of them have been dated between 16th to 17th century AD. Thus, it is concluded herewith that the composition of this text could not have been prior to the date of *Ekāmrapurāṇa* and *Kapilasamhitā*.” - Acharya, Anil Kumar, 2019, pp.172-173

two, the palm-leaf manuscript of OSM is complete; but in a bad condition as many folios are worm eaten. The GOML manuscript is an incomplete one, because only thirty-four out of forty chapters are found therein. On internal and external evidence, viz. citations from well-known Śaiva texts of Odisha, usages of Odia words, availability of a Śaivāmṛtsārasamuccaya manuscript in Odisha, etc., it has been believed that this text might have been of Odishan origin.⁶ An edition of this text on the basis of above mentioned two manuscripts has been undertaken by me and is under process.

A careful, comprehensive, and comparative study of these above-mentioned Śaiva scriptures proper of Odisha could open up new facts about Odishan Śaivism and its relation with pan-Indian Śaiva tradition. In pursuit of the same, let us now explore the presence of Śivadharmā and Śivadharmottara, two important pan-Indian Śaiva texts, in the Śaiva scriptures of Odisha.

Traces of Śivadharmā and Śivadharmottara:

There is a Śivadharmottara *Purāṇam* manuscript, with no. P/373, in the Orissa State Museum, which is mentioned in the 'An alphabetical catalogue of Sanskrit Manuscripts', Part-I, Ed. by Sri Nilamani Mishra, published in the year 1973 (p. 84, MS Sl. No. 793). Unfortunately, it could not be traced in the Descriptive Catalogue of Sanskrit Manuscripts of Orissa, Vol. III, Purāṇa manuscripts. But on physical verification of the images of the said manuscript collected from Orissa State Museum, it was found that this manuscript contains both Śivadharmā and Śivadharmottara texts, and some folios are in damaged condition.

Also *An alphabetical catalogue of Oriya & Other Manuscripts*, Ed. by Nilamani Mishra, 1972, mentions two manuscripts titled Śivottara *Purāṇa* and Śaivottara *Purāṇa* with numbers OrP/1174 and OrP/1096 respectively, and the authorship of both have

6 "But there are few facts noticed during the study of this text which are closely associated with Utkala/Kaliṅga, i.e. present day Odisha. Those facts are: 1. Citations from Ekāmrapurāṇa and Kapilasamhitā, two well known śaivite paurāṇic literature of Odisha, and citation from Śātānandasāṅgraha written by famous Sanskrit scholar Satānda Acharya (1099 AD) of Odisha. 2. Usages of the Odia word nula and karatāḥ instead of Sanskrit form kartārah. 3. Availability of manuscripts in Odisha, which has been mentioned at the beginning. 4. The presence of Hari-Hara cult predominately in Odisha." - *ibid*, p.190

been attributed to Bhagirathi Das (Mishra 1972, 117). These two manuscripts, I assume, could be the text Śivadharmottara. I have yet to physically see these above mentioned two Odia Purāṇa manuscripts and their contents to substantiate my assumption.

Besides, it has been observed that Śivadharmā and Śivadharmottara have been mentioned, directly or indirectly, in most of the above mentioned Śaiva texts of Odisha.

Ekāmra Purāṇa does not mention Śivadharmā and Śivadharmottara in its list of eighteen *Purāṇas* and *upa-purāṇas* (*Ekāmra Purāṇa*, chapter 1, verses 17-24); but mentions the word Śivadharmā with the seventh case ending in its fifth part, chapter no. sixty-three, the second half of the verse no thirty-four, which reads - śivadharmeṣu ye'abhijñā vaiśeṣika-vinirṇayā||34|| sidhyanti siddhayo vyagrā āgamoktā pṛthakvidhā||35||⁷. And mentions Śivadharmottara in its twenty-second chapter, instructing to follow the yogic practice as prescribed in Śivadharmottara⁸. Also, *Ekāmra Purāṇa* narrates sixty-eight *tīrthas* -Śaiva sacred places for pilgrimage- (chapter 61, verses 50-60) which includes the old *pañcāṣṭakas* (forty Śaiva sacred places for pilgrimage), described in the Śivadharmā corpus and *Skanda Purāṇa* etc.

Ekāmracandrikā mentions Śaivottara/ Śivottara at least twice in its ninth chapter, which reads - śaivottare purāṇe tu sṛṇudhvaṁ bho muniśvarāḥ|1| śivottare dvijaśreṣṭhāḥ sṛṇudhvaṁ samivadamī vaḥ|23| (Mishra 1995, 48-50). As has been assumed above, this Śaivottara/ Śivottara might be none other than the text Śivadharmottaram of Śivadharmā corpus.

Śaivacintāmaṇi in its last chapter, i.e. eighth *paṭala*, mentions that there is no great scripture than Śivadharmāśāstra, which reads - Śivadharmamṛte na sāstramanyat śivaliṅgamṛte na devatā'aste|71| (Pattanayak 186) Śaivakalpdruma which recapitulates the Śaivaite tradition of Odisha quotes Śivadharmā and Śivadharmottara

7. Dhal, Upendranath, 1986, pp. 425-26; this verse has been cited and commented upon in the Śaivakalpdruma which reads - तथा एकाम्रपुराणे - शिवधर्मे च योभिज्ञानै शैक्षिकविनिर्णयः । सिद्ध्यन्ति सिद्धयोव्यग्रा आगमोक्ताः पृथग्विधाः ॥ सम्भवन्ति न लीयन्ते ईश्वराणामिति स्मृताः । ये शिवधर्मशास्त्रे पूर्वोत्तरसहितेभिज्ञाः पण्डिताः । तेषामेव आगमोक्तां सिद्धयो व्यग्राः सिद्ध्यन्ति । ते भवनेन सम्भवन्ते । ईश्वराणामंशतो लीयन्ते सायुज्यं प्राप्नुवन्तीत्यर्थः । शिवधर्मशास्त्राभ्यासफलमेव दर्शितम् । अतस्तन्मागौणैव शिवाश्रयः कर्तव्यः । MS, p.63

8 शिवयोग समासाच्च शिवधर्मोत्तरोदितम् । अक्षये शिवलोके तु शिवेन सह मोदते ॥96 ॥

profusely. Let us discuss the presence of Śivadharmā and Śivadharmottara through citations in the eight chapters of Śaivakalpadrūma. In its first chapter (*kāṇḍa*) Śivadharmā has been cited thrice⁹ and Śivadharmottara once¹⁰. In its second chapter Śivadharmā has been cited twice, once in the context of *dakṣiṇāmūrtiṅgalakṣaṇa*¹¹ and again in the context of *mālānirṇaya (rudrākṣamāhātmya)*¹². Śivadharmottara has been quoted twice, first in support of the fact that ‘*śivapañcākṣaramantra* is a *vaidikamantra*’¹³ and secondly while defining various kinds of *japas*¹⁴, viz. *vyakta*, *upāṃśu* and *mānasa*. The third chapter cites passages from around thirty- five texts and among them, Śivadharmā and Śivadharmottara are oft-quoted texts. Śivadharmā has been quoted around twelve times and Śivadharmottara ten times in this chapter. And it is worthy to mention here that in this 3rd chapter Lakshmidhara, the author of Śaivakalpadrūma, has mentioned that the Śivadharmā together with its later part Śivadharmottara consists of twenty-four chapters¹⁵. He advocates that these are two authoritative texts for Śaivas, and once explaining a cited line from *Skandapurāṇa* Lakshmidhara had mentioned that these texts are Pāśupata texts¹⁶. In the fourth chapter Śivadharmā has been cited

9. तथा च शिवधर्मे – दक्षिणाङ्गाद्भवेद्ब्रह्मा हरिर्वामाङ्गसम्भवः । हृदयान्निर्गतो रुद्रो ब्रह्मविष्णुप्रबोधकः ॥ जगत्सृष्टिकरो ब्रह्मा विष्णुर्लोकविमोहकः । अनुग्रहकरो नित्यं नीलो रुद्रः शिवात्मकः ॥ - MS, p. 5; शिवधर्मे – अ . . मातात्परो देवः शिवः परमकारणम् । तस्मादेतत्समुत्पन्नं जगतः कारणत्नयम् ॥ - MS, p.6; तथा च शिवधर्मे – ब्रह्मा च पूजयेत्लिङ्गं नित्यं शैलमयं पुरा । तस्य सम्पूजनात्तेन प्राप्तं ब्रह्मत्वमुत्तमम् ॥ इन्द्रनीलमयं लिङ्गं विष्णुर ईयते सदा । विष्णुत्वं प्राप्तवांस्तेन अच्युतैकसनातनम् ॥ शक्तोपि देवराजेन्द्रो लिङ्गं मणिमयं स्मृतम् । भक्त्या पूजयते नित्यं तेन शक्रत्वमाप्नुयात् ॥ - MS, p.13
10. तथा च शिवधर्मोत्तरखण्डे – एवं त्रयोपि रागाद्यैर्दोषैर्देवैः समन्विताः । एभ्यः परश्शिवः शान्तः परिपूर्णः समुक्तिदः ॥ MS, p.6
11. दक्षिणामूर्तिशब्दस्य व्याख्यामाह शिवधर्मे - वामदेवानं यत्र तत्र गौरीजनार्दनौ । दक्षिणेस्य यतो मूर्तिर्दक्षिणामूर्तिरीरिता ॥ MS, p.22
12. तथा च शिवधर्मे रुद्राक्षमाहात्म्ये - जपश्च रुद्रमन्त्राणां कोटिकोटिगुणोत्तरम् । MS, p.25
13. वेदे शिवागमे चैव उभयत्र षडाक्षरम् । मन्त्रस्थितः सतां मुक्त्यै लोके पापाक्षरस्थितः [पञ्चाक्षरस्थितः] ॥ इति शिवधर्मोत्तर- वचनात्, रुद्राध्याये नमः शावाय च शिवतत्पराय चेति वचनाद्वा वैदिकोऽयमवगम्यते . . . । MS, p.20
14. शिवधर्मोत्तरे - यदुच्चनीचस्वरितैः शब्दैः स्पष्टपदाक्षरैः । मन्त्रमुच्चारयेद्वाचा जपयज्ञः स वाचिकः ॥ शनैरुच्चारयेन्मन्त्र- मीषदोष्टौ प्रचालयेत् । किञ्चित्सन्ध्यास्त्वयं विद्यादुपांशुस्तज्जपं स्मृतम् ॥ धिया पदाक्षरश्रेण्या वर्णाद्वर्णं पदत्पदम् । शब्दार्थ-चिन्तनाद्यं यत्तदुक्तं मानसं जपम् ॥..... MS, p.28
15. तथा शिवधर्मे - शिवधर्मपराः शान्ताः शिवध्यानपरायणाः । सर्व एवाश्रया ज्ञेयाः शिवभक्ताः शिवाश्रयाः ॥ शिवधर्मे शिवधर्मशास्त्रे पूर्वोत्तरचतुर्विंशत्याध्याये परायणा निरताः । अनेनापि शिवधर्मशास्त्रालोकनं तदुक्तकृत्यं वैशानामावश्यकमुक्तम् । MS, pp.62-63
16. स्कन्दपुराणे – शिवधर्मोदितान् शौचान् शैव- कुर्यात्तु नित्यदा । वैष्णवं पाशुपतमिति शिवधर्मोत्तरशास्त्रमेव देवैः समा मन्त्रयेत् । अतः शैवानां शिवधर्मशास्त्रमार्गाक्तधर्म एवाश्रयणीय इत्यर्थः । तच्छास्त्रमार्गानुगामिनां फलं दर्शयति । - MS, p.74

five times. The fifth chapter cites Śivadharma thirty-seven times, and Śivadharmottara ten times on varied topics. Śivadharma has been cited seven times in the sixth chapter. The seventh chapter cites Śivadharma ten times. In the eighth chapter quotes Śivadharma twelve times. In this way, it shows that in the seventeenth century Śivadharma and Śivadharmottara were well known in Odisha and had been followed by the Śaiva priests of Ekāmraṅṣetra.

Śivāmṛtsārasamuccaya cites Śivadharma twenty-seven times and Śivadharmottara five times. Citations of Śivadharma and Śivadharmottara in Śivāmṛtsārasamuccaya are found between fourteenth to thirty-fifth chapters. In its fourteenth chapter Śivadharma has been cited twice in the context of the worship of different types of *pārthiva-liṅgas* by various Gods, viz. Brahmā, Viṣṇu etc.¹⁷, and interestingly these passages are found to be existent in the 3rd chapter of the presently available Śivadharmaśāstram text. In the fifteenth chapter, passages from Śivadharma have been cited twice in the context of *pūjāphala*¹⁸ and *trikālapūjā*¹⁹ and those cited passages are found in the fifth, seventh and eighth chapters of Śivadharmaśāstram. Śivadharma has been cited once in the sixteenth chapter in the context of describing the different auspicious times for the worship of Śiva²⁰, and the same passages are found existent in the seventh chapter of Śivadharmaśāstra. Describing the ritual bathing of a Śiva-*liṅga* by different materials, Śivadharma has been cited four

- 17 अथ विशेषलिङ्गार्चनमाह शिवधर्मे - यः कुर्यात् पार्थिवं लिङ्गमर्चयेत् सर्वदेव हि । इहैव धनवान् श्रीमान् सोऽपि रुद्रोभिजायते ॥1 ॥ -MS, p.24; शिवधर्मे - ब्रह्मा पूजयते नित्यं लिङ्गं शैलमयं शुभम् । तस्य सम्पूजनात्तेन प्राप्तं ब्रह्मत्वमुत्तमम् ॥7 ॥ इन्द्रनीलमयं लिङ्गं विष्णुरर्चयते सदा । विष्णुत्वं प्राप्तवान् तेन अच्युतैकसनातनम् ॥8 ॥ शक्रोऽपि देवराजेन्द्रो लिङ्गं मणिमयं कृतम् । भक्त्या पूजयते नित्यं तेन शक्रत्वमाप्नुयात् ॥9 ॥ ताम्रलिङ्गं सदाकालं भक्त्या देवो दिवाकरः । समभ्यर्च्य ततस्तेन प्राप्तं सूर्यत्वमुत्तमम् ॥10 ॥ कुबेरः काञ्चनमयं लिङ्गमभ्यर्चिते सदा । तेनासौ धनदः श्रीमान् मानवैः परिगीयते ॥11 ॥ MS, pp.25-26.
- 18 शिवधर्मे - यावन्नाभ्येति मरणं यावन्नाक्रमते जराः । यावन्नाद्रियते कैवल्यं तावत्पूजय शङ्करम् ॥17 ॥ न शैशवश्च [शैवश्च-conj.] धर्मोऽस्ति तुल्योऽन्यो भुवनत्रये । इति विज्ञाय यत्नेन पूजनीयः सदाशिवः ॥18 ॥ MS, p.28
- 19 लिकालार्चनमाह - शिवधर्मे - प्रातरुत्थाय यो लिङ्गं भक्त्या सम्पूजयेत् सकृत् । कपिलायाः शतं ह[द-ed.]त्वा यत्फलं दत्तमाप्नुयात् [तदवाप्नुयात्-ed.] ॥21 ॥ तथा - मध्यं दिनकरे प्राप्ते यो लिङ्गं प्रतिपूजयेत् । सम्पूर्णं पृथिवीं दत्त्वा यत्फलं तदवाप्नुयात् ॥22 ॥ तथा - वारुणामिन्त्रितेः सूर्ये यः शिवं सम्यगर्चयेत् । गवां शतसहस्रस्य दत्तस्य फलमाप्नुयात् ॥23 ॥ मासि मासि च योऽश्रीयात् यवान्नं व्रतमुत्तमम् । यश्चार्चयेत् सकृद्विङ्गं सममेतन् न संशयः ॥24 ॥ यः प्रदद्याद्गवां लक्षं दोग्ध्रीणां वेदपारगो । एकाहमर्चयेद्विङ्गं तस्य पुण्यं ततोऽधिकम् ॥25 ॥ सस्नातः सर्वतीर्थेषु स सर्वोपरि संस्थितः । यः पूजयेन्महादेवं लिङ्गं सर्वार्थसाधकम् ॥26 ॥ MS, pp.28-29.
- 20 शिवधर्मे - नैरन्त्येण षण्मासं विधिना पूजयेच्छिवम् । पुण्यं तदेव सकले लभते विषुवाचनात् ॥4 ॥ एते देवविज्ञेयं ग्रहणे चोत्तरायणे । संक्रान्तिषु दिने छिद्रे षडस्याति मुखेषु च ॥5 ॥ मासे श्वतुर्भिर्मृत्युण्यं विधिना पुज्य शङ्करम् । तत्कार्तिक्यां भवेत्युण्यं पौर्णमास्यां विशेषतः ॥6 ॥ MS, pp.30-31.

times in the eighteenth chapter²¹, and those are found existent in the fifth chapter of Śivadharmaśāstram. Śivadharma has been cited in the nineteenth chapter in the context of describing merits to be obtained by performing a dance, music etc. during the worship of Śiva²², and the cited passages are existent in the eighth chapter of Śivadharmaśāstram. Twenty-second chapter cites passages from Śivadharma thrice in the context of describing offerings of different flowers and leaves to Śiva²³, and, except the verse no. thirty-four, all other verses cited in this chapter from Śivadharma are found existent in the fifth chapter of Śivadharmaśāstram. A line from Śivadharmottara has been cited in the twenty-third chapter in the context of *dhūpadānaphala*²⁴, and the same is found in the second chapter of Śivadharmottaram. Twenty-fifth chapter quotes two verses from Śivadharmottara²⁵; of those, verse no. thirteen is found in the fourth chapter of the presently available Śivadharmottaram. The twenty-sixth chapter cites Śivadharmottara once in the context of *prāṇāyāmadhyāna*²⁶. In the context of śivapañcakṣara-*mantra* two verses have been cited from Śivadharma in the twenty-seventh chapter²⁷, and those are found existent with slight variation in

- 21 शिवधर्मे - स्नाप्य लिङ्गं सकृद्ब्रह्मा विष्णुलोके महीयते ॥13॥ MS, p.33; शिवधर्मे - नैरन्तर्येण यो मासं घृतस्नानं समाचरेत् । एकविंशशुक्रलोपेतो यान्ति वै शङ्करालयम् ॥20॥ MS, p.34; शिवधर्मे - कपिलापञ्चगव्येन कुशवारियुतेन च । स्नापयेन्मन्त्रयुक्तेन ब्रह्मस्नाने हि त्कलम् ॥30॥ एकाहमपि यो लिङ्गं ब्रह्मस्नानं समाचरेत् । विधूय सर्वपापानि शिवलोके महीयते ॥31॥ MS, p.35; शिवधर्मे - कुशोदकेन यो लिङ्गं सकृदास्नापयेन्नरः । काञ्चनेन विमानेन रुद्रलोके महीयते ॥38॥ वस्त्रपूतेन तोयेन यो नरः स्नापयेत्सकृत् । सर्वकामैस्तु संपूर्णं वारुणं लोकमाप्नुयात् ॥39॥ मन्त्राष्टशतजपेन विमलेनाम्भसा शिवम् । स्नापयित्वा सकृद्भक्त्या शिवलोकमवाप्नुयात् ॥40॥ पितृनुद्दिश्य यो लिङ्गं स्नापयेच्छित्तवारिणा । तृप्ताः स्वर्गं गमिष्यन्ति पितरो नरकादपि ॥41॥ MS, pp.35-36.
- 22 शिवधर्मे - भूमिदानेन यत्पुण्यं च .?[गो-conj.] दानेन यत्कलम् । मुखवाद्येन तत्सर्वमुभयं लभते नरः ॥8॥ तदेव पुण्यं गीतस्य नृत्यस्य च विशेषतः । तदेवं जयशब्दस्य तदेवं तालकध्वने ॥9॥ MS, p.38.
- 23 शिवधर्मे - पुष्पैररण्यसम्भूतैः पालैर्वा गिरिसंभवैः । अपर्युषितनिश्चिदैः पौक्षितैर्जन्तुवर्जितः ॥12॥ आत्मारामो भवेत्पुष्पैः पतैः सम्पूजयेच्छिवम् । पुष्पजातिमशेषेण भवेत्पुण्यमशेषतः ॥13॥ तपः शीलगुणोपेते . . . दस्युः[सर्ववेदस्य - conj.] पारगे । सुवर्णकोटिं दत्त्वा तु यत्फलं देवमाप्नुयात् ॥14॥ MS, pp.43-44; शिवधर्मे - तुलसीपुत्रागतकौलनागवक्रकृत्सरिभः । कुरुवकशिरिषशिशुपा- गिरिमल्लिका ॥33॥ यज्ञवक्षुपुष्पकिरातजपा मधुतिलाम्रच्छातुवणातरुक्षपालाशसौगन्धिक- दाडिमकृशमाण्डककटी- राजजटाकिशुकुरक्तचित्त-चम्पक कुरु कोकिलाक्ष । कोविदारकसुम्भककरञ्जक पद्मकरवीरादिनि पुष्पाणि नाना पुराणोक्तम् नेपाली वराहदंष्ट्र शैललोध्रास्ति मुचुकुन्दप्रियङ्गुधान्य रक्तोत्पलम् ॥34॥ - MS, pp.45-46; शिवधर्मे - यः सुगन्धैः मुक्तपुष्पैः सम्यग्लिङ्गं प्रपूजयेत् । मालाभिर्वापि सुघनैः सोऽन्ते फलमवाप्नुयात् ॥43॥ MS, pp.46-47.
- 24 शिवधर्मोत्तरे - तुरुष्पागरुकर्पूरैः शिवचन्दनगुग्गुलैः ॥10॥ MS, p.52.
- 25 शिवधर्मोत्तरे - क्षीरयुक्तेन नैवेद्यं दशकोटिगुणाधिकम् । शर्करादधिसेयुक्तं तत्पुण्यं स्याद्दशाधिकम् ॥13॥ पायसं घृतसंपूर्णं तु विशिष्टान्न, व्यञ्जनपाकरसालतिलमोदनम् । आरोणक्षीरप्रवासादिनादानानस्य फलमनैकम् ॥14॥ MS, p.56.
- 26 अथ प्राणायाममध्यानाह - शिवधर्मोत्तरे - उपावियोनितप्यन्ते? यज्ञदानव्रतानि च । सर्वतीर्थाभिषेकञ्च प्राणायामश्च तत्समम् ॥1॥ MS, p.58.
- 27 शिवधर्मे - सर्वदा सर्वकार्येषु युतनष्टावनादिषु । तस्मै नमः शिवायेति शिवभक्तः शिवं व्रजेत् ॥6॥ यो नमः

the seventh chapter of presently available Śivadharmaśāstram. Śivadharma has been mentioned in the twenty-ninth chapter in the context of describing the benefit of offering obeisance to Śiva after circumambulation²⁸. Thirtieth chapter cites Śivadharmottara²⁹ once in the context of *dānaphala*, and long passages from Śivadharma eight times in the context of describing the importance of donation of different things to Lord Śiva and the benefits of doing so. Verses cited from Śivadharmottara are found in the second chapter of presently available Śivadharmottaram, and almost all passages cited from Śivadharma are found available in the fourth, fifth, eighth and tenth chapters of the presently available Śivadharmaśāstram. Both Śivadharma and Śivadharmottara have been quoted in the thirty-third chapter describing different rewards obtained by building an abode for Lord Śiva³⁰. It is worthy to mention herein that cited Śivadharmottara verses are not found in the presently available Śivadharmottaram; rather those along with cited passages from Śivadharma are found existent in the fourth chapter of the presently available Śivadharmaśāstram. The last chapter, i.e. the thirty-fifth chapter, cites Śivadharma thrice describing the holiness of the surroundings of the Śiva temple³¹.

In this context, it is necessary to mention herein that the authenticity of the cited verses from Śivadharma and Śivadharmottara in Śivāmṛtsārasamuccaya has been examined by searching and comparing those passages in the available editions of Śivadharma and Śivadharmottara. Those editions are Yogi Narahari Nath's edition of Śivadharma corpus titled *Paśupatiṃtam* Śivadharma-

प्रतिबन्धस्तु प्रा । न्तेन? सकृदस्मरन् । नमः शिवायेति मन्त्रः स गतिः परमं पदम् ॥7 ॥ MS, p.59.

- 28 शिवधर्म - या संख्या तस्य रेणूनां स्पृशन्ति पाणिपादयोः । तावद्बर्षसहस्राणि रुद्रलोके महीयते ॥7 ॥ MS, p.66.
- 29 शिवधर्मोत्तरे - यावदक्षरसंख्या तु शिवशास्त्रेषु पुस्तकम् । दशवर्षसहस्राणि दाता शिवपुरं वसेत् ॥3 ॥ तथा - सान्तःपुरं परिवारः सर्वभूत्यसमन्वितः । दिव्यं शिवपुरं गच्छेद्द्विद्यादानप्रभावतः ॥4 ॥ MS, pp.67-68.
- 30 शिवधर्म - मृदा वेष्टकशैलं वा पश्चात्कुर्याच्छिवालये । त्रिसप्तकुलसंयुक्तः रुद्रलोके महीयते ॥1 ॥ - MS, p.90; शिवधर्मोत्तरे - मृन्मयाः कोटिगुणितं फलं स्याद्दारुभिः कृतम् । कोटिकोटिगुणं पुण्यं दारुवा[व-conj.] दिष्टकालये ॥7 ॥ इष्टकादिगुणं पुण्यं शैलेयस्याच्छिवालये । इष्टसुसमायुतवत् सौंषपि कुर्याच्छिवालये ॥8 ॥ विधूतपापसंघातं सगच्छेच्छुचालयम् ॥9 ॥ - MS, p.91; शिवधर्म - यावद . नि[यावदहनि-conj.] कुरुते धवलं तच्छिवालये । तावद्बर्षसहस्राणि शिवलोके महीयते ॥12 ॥ -MS, p.91.
- 31 शिवधर्म - ग्रामे वा यदि वारण्ये जले वापि स्थलेपि वा । यन्नैव दृश्यते लिङ्गं सर्वतीर्थानि तत्र वै ॥8 ॥ -MS, p.94; शिवधर्म - आरामं चावसं कूपं तटाकं देवतागृहम् । शिवक्षेत्रेषु यः कुर्यात्सोऽनन्तफलमाप्नुयात् ॥11 ॥ गृहे श्राद्धस्य यत्पुण्यं मरणे तच्छताधिकम् । शिवाश्रमेषु विज्ञेयं तत्पुण्यम्युताधिकम् ॥12 ॥ -MS, p.94; शिवधर्म - शिवक्षेत्रसमीपस्थं यत्तयोः पुरतस्थितम् । शिवगङ्गादकं ज्ञेयं तत्र सात्वा शिवं व्रजेत् ॥19 ॥ -MS, p.95.

mahāśāstram *Paśupati-nāthadarśanam*, Śivadharmasāstram (Śivadharmā-pūrvam) - a paper transcript bearing no. T32 of the French Institute of Pondicherry, Śivadharmottaram - a paper transcript bearing no. T75 of the French Institute of Pondicherry and Srikrishna 'Jugnu' & Bhanvar Sharma's edition of Śivadharmā titled ŚrimadŚivadharmapurāṇam.

Besides, it has been observed that Odia *smṛti* writer Narasimha Vajapeyi has cited *Śivadharmā* in his *Nityācārapradīpa*³² in the context of the definition of *pañcagavya* and its holiness. And it has been mentioned in the Descriptive Catalogue of Sanskrit Manuscripts in Orissa, Vol. I, that *Śivadharmottara* has been quoted by Purusottamadeva in his *Mukticintāmaṇi* (Mahapatra 1958, 79), a manuscript of which has been preserved in Orissa state museum with no. P.29 (b). Also, it has been noted in the Descriptive Catalogue Sanskrit Manuscripts, Vol. VII, that the text *Kṛṣṇabhaktikalpalatā*, with no. Dh/298 in Orissa state museum, which has been attributed to Jagannātha Das has quoted *Śivadharmottara* (Mishra 1971, 35).

From the above deliberations on the traces of *Śivadharmā* and *Śivadharmottara* in the Śaiva scriptures of Odisha, and presence of a manuscript of *Śivadharmā* corpus in general and *Śivadharmā* & *Śivadharmottara* in special in the Orissa State Museum are indicative of the fact that *Śivadharmā* and *Śivadharmottara* were known to the saivites of ancient Odisha. Thus, the importance of *Śivadharmā* and *Śivadharmottara* in the context of Śaivism in Odisha is undeniable.

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32 शिवधर्मो - पञ्चामृतं दधिक्षीरशितामधुघृतं नृप । गोमूत्रं गोमयं क्षीरं दधि सर्पिः कुशोदकम् । पञ्चगव्यमिति प्रोक्तं सर्वपापप्रणाशनम् ॥-नित्याचारप्रदीप, p.238.

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